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Title

Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization

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Abstract

Developing a community's local tourism has always been regarded as a sustainable tool in contributing to an equitable sharing of benefits among the stakeholders, apart from the appreciation visitors achieve from partaking on a destination's local tourism efforts. Local tourism assets may come in different forms from natural to something that is organized and held on identified community sites. This qualitative study described the Mangkelleb Hill of Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya as a pilgrimage site since the start of its initial development up to its current state, the challenges the management encountered to have it developed as a known pilgrimage site in the province, and eventually yielded a recommended plan of actions for the realization of the project's further development. The responses of key stakeholders through interviews and focus group discussions from the community where the site is located were solicited providing answers to the set objectives. The study was conducted in the first semester of the academic year 2024-2025 and it likewise endeavored to unfold the key elements that contribute and may further continue to support a desired level or extent of partnership among key stakeholders to achieve set goals in relation to a community project anchored on religious and tourism purposes and activities.

Keywords: local tourism, religious tourism, pilgrimage site, community-based sustainable tourism (CBST)

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Introduction

A. Short Introduction

Developing a community's local tourism has always been regarded as a sustainable tool in contributing to an equitable sharing of benefits among the stakeholders, apart from the appreciation visitors achieve from partaking in a destination's local tourism efforts. As such, there are four (4) rural tourism contributions or benefits, and these are economic, socio-cultural, environmental, leisure, and educational perspectives (Liu, Chiang & Ko, 2023). With these 4 rural tourism benefits, there are a total of 32 specific benefits that can be gained in local tourism. Based on the study conducted by Liu, Chiang & Ko (2023), the economic benefit is an important perspective that rural tourism can have on the site. In support, the UN World Tourism Organization (n.d.) recognized that rural tourism has a high potential to stimulate local economic growth and social change because of its complementarity with economic benefits. As defined by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), rural tourism activities take place in non-urban or rural areas which has low population density, landscape and land use dominated by agriculture and forestry, and traditional social structure and lifestyle. Last May 30 to June 1, 2023, a seminar conducted by the Department of Science and Technology – Food and Fertilizer Technology Center focused on harnessing the economic and sociocultural opportunities of rural and farm tourism. The seminar addressed and gave a platform to discuss this emerging rural tourism engagement, in terms of its potential and challenges and as a strategy for boosting rural areas in generating income after the CoVID-19 pandemic. In support of this, last June 29, 2023, the Department of Tourism released a new tourism slogan, **Love the Philippines**. The new slogan encapsulates unending reasons for loving the Philippines. DOT Secretary Frasco said (in verbatim) “the verbalization of enjoyment was love”. Love that focused on new and authentic real-world experiences, which means immersing in other cultures and seeking curated experiences that are unique or out of the ordinary. And so, the new tourism slogan is focused on the varied tourism assets the country has, including different rural tourism sites and activities. Which, therefore, may encompass all the other forms of tourism, including religious tourism for this matter.

In the case of Nueva Vizcaya, numerous attractions both natural and man-made are included in the inventory of tourism attractions as collated by the Provincial Local Government Unit (PLGU). Some of these attractions are owned and managed by the government sector itself, while many man-made are privately owned ventures. Being a province that is rich with stories from the past, some notable attractions are rooted in history, the people's culture, and even religion. The Catholic churches from each of the towns for example, share their stories of how they had weathered

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natural events in the past but had been renovated and beautified over the years making them frequently visited by the residents as many are Catholics, and to include visitors. During the holy week or the Lenten season, these churches are the main attractions for the Visita Iglesia, and also pilgrimage sites with the re-enactment of the Passion of the Christ taking place in Bangan Hill National Park in the town of Bayombong, for example. Apart from Bayombong, the town of Villaverde also has its Mangkelleb Hill as a venue for Good Friday's re-enactment of Christ's Passion, the second time this year 2024, that the event took place in it. The Hill is owned and managed by the Our Lady of Fatima Parish of Villaverde. The gradual improvement of the site is basically led by the parish with the efforts of some church and community members. However, it is noted that much can be done to have in place a maximized and beautified pilgrimage site that will truly stand out from among the attractions in the province. It is with this observation that the researchers intend to work on studying the Mangkelleb Hill, particularly by describing it as a pilgrimage site, note its challenges encountered to have it developed as a known pilgrimage site in the province, and craft a recommended plan of actions for the realization of the project's further development. Further, this study is aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UNSDG) number 17, Partnerships for the Goals where it is seen that tapping multi-sectoral participation is necessary in combining efforts relative to further development and maintenance of a locally promoted, parish-owned site for the benefit of the greater community, and the UNSDG number 11. This is about providing access to sustainable cities and communities to ensure access to all the benefits by the community members and stakeholders brought by the tourism activities in the pilgrimage site.

B. RRL and RS of Major Concepts / Variables (Based on Problem)

Tourism Revitalization

Revitalization refers to giving new life, energy, activity, or success to something (Cambridge Dictionary, N.D.). In the study of Childres (2021), revitalization was defined as "make alive again". Which means, restoring the declining interest to a healthy and growing state. With the global Corona Virus Disease 19 (CoViD-19) pandemic in March 2020, all tourist and travel related activities and engagements came to a halt. This includes, pilgrimage and religious Tourism being affected by this global crisis. Mroz (2021), presented 90-95% decline of pilgrimage movement during this time. With the devastating effects of the CoVid-19, it left many repercussions for tourism industry. In the results from the study of Baloch, Maher, Shah, Sheeraz, Iqbal, and Raza (2022), revitalization through responsiveness, use of advance technology, customers', and employees' willingness, enhance skills, adherence to standard operating procedures and protective measure, restructuring

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via a public-private partnerships were drawn as a solution to depleting pilgrimage and religious tourism. On the other hand, Seraphine & Jarraud (2022) said that the global crisis brought by CoVid-19 brought opportunities to the tourism industry, wherein there were online versions of visiting different pilgrimage sites, and thereafter, further development came during lockdowns. The Catholic Bishops' Conference of the Philippines (CBCP), the Catholic Liturgists said that, "one way to promote a synodal spirit is through pilgrimages". To deepen the faith of Liturgists, the Catholic Liturgists of the Philippines urged the dioceses and parishes, to advocate pilgrimages as a means of evangelization (Escover, 2023). Moreover, CBCP defined pilgrimage as a religious journey where people pray together and listen to each other as they walk to a particular sacred destination.

Development of tourism is difficult to understand without a thorough comprehension of the practices of the pilgrimage site in the past many years (Collins-Kreiner, 2020). Hence, the researchers include also the conduct of initial site assessments to know the different practices, history and developments of the Mangkeleb Hill, the Our Lady of Victory Pilgrimage site. At some point, though the concerned hill of this study has not yet achieved maximized development, the site is seen to be something of a destination leading to be one of the key sites or attractions in the town, as venue for pilgrimages. Therefore, apart from contributing to the inventory of tourism resources or assets in the town, it is also a good case for community-based sustainable tourism.

Pilgrimage Tourism

Pilgrimage tourism is regarded to be one of the oldest types of tourism being practiced in the earliest times. This type of tourism is defined as a process of visiting pilgrimage sites and religious destinations like churches, mosques, and other landmarks that motivate tourists to achieve religious attitudes and practices (Stainton, 2023). A pilgrimage tourist is on a journey to a holy place, which includes reasons such as trade conquest, education, and leisure (Zarb, 2020).

Moreover, pilgrimage tourism involves traveling to sacred sites for spiritual fulfillment, blending traditional religious journeys with modern secular experiences. Recent studies highlight its evolving nature, emphasizing diverse motivations and emerging destinations, reflecting broader trends in spirituality and cultural exchange (Papallou, Katafygiotou, & Dimopoulos, 2024). Hence, Collins-Kreiner (2022) described pilgrimage tourism by its 2 Key characteristics: Spiritual Motivations and Cultural and Historical Significance.

The Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto site also known as the *Mangkelleb* is an emerging pilgrimage tourism site among church goers from the town of Villaverde especially during the holy week particularly on Good Friday. From the

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initial site visits of the researchers, it was noticed that the visitors are driven by their faith and some for the scenic view on top of the pilgrimage site.

These pilgrimage activities are often long and sometimes difficult, but they also bring benefits to pilgrims like a chance to reflect, arrive at a certain religious enlightenment, or adjust after a loss as a way to heal. It also gives way to deepen the relationship with their religion by showing dedication to their faith (Stainton, 2023). However, pilgrimage activities, for some, can also be as brief as an excursion or a day, provided that the purpose, which is religious in nature, is present. Churches and monasteries for example in Valcea County in South-West Oltenia Region, Romania are also for religious tourism and pilgrimage purpose and are representing major historical and cultural elements for the location's identity and attractiveness (Drăguleasa, Niță, Mazilu, & Constantinescu, 2024). In other locations, visits to sites for religious and pilgrimage tourism purposes are also growing in interest. This is also true in the case of Slovakia, wherein attendance analysis revealed a significant upward trend on sacred sites (Jesensky, Kornecka, Molokac, & Tometzova, 2024). This implies collaboration is necessary in ensuring the sustainability of historically significant sites for further local development.

Role of Communities in Pilgrimage Sites

The local residents of pilgrimage sites play a very important role in maintaining the location. The success of community-based tourism depends also on the level of awareness and ownership of the local community. In addition, the community needs to play as the host that welcomes and offers pilgrims, and travelers a sense of belonging and hospitality. Because a real visitor experience remains authentic only when religious activities have strong participation by the local community, and not at some other stage (Zarb, 2020). Through pilgrimage tourism, communities benefit from the tourism activities. In the study conducted by Tendero (2023) in the Fort Pilar Shrine in Zamboanga, they found out that the local community benefited significantly from the local economy through employment opportunities and economic development.

Liu, Chiang & Ko (2023) also shared that tourism contributes to economic, socio-cultural, environmental, leisure, and educational benefits, especially to the local community. Zivrali (2022) also shared additional benefits like a self-sustained and locally managed economy, local knowledge for preservation and sustainability, active participation and community involvement in decision-making and the increasing value and protection of the local culture. Thus, the role of local community members has a symbiotic relationship with the site itself.

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Elements/Components of a Pilgrimage Site

In the Philippines, one of the notable religious sites is the Monasterio de Tarlac, a Catholic monastery and eco-tourism park that was constructed in 2003 at the Mt. Resurrection. It houses a relic believed to be a fragment of the True Cross of Jesus Christ (Zozobrado, 2022). Another shrine is the Kamay ni Hesus located in Lucban, Quezon. This shrine is located at the foot of Mt. Banahaw where Rev. Fr. Joseph Ayala Faller precedes his healing masses for all devotees, averaging 300,000 visitors annually. The shrine is also known for its 50-foot Ascending Christ statue and the grotto with statues of the Stations of the Cross (Sanchez, 2022).

Other pilgrimage sites were shared by Sorilla IV (2019), where he identified some of the must-visit popular pilgrimage sites in the Philippines. These are the St. John the Baptist Parish Church in Manila, Simala Shrine in Cebu, Minor Basilica of the Our Lady of the Most Holy Rosary of Pangasinan, San Pascual de Baylon Parish Church in Bulacan, National Shrine and Parish of St. Padre Pio in Batangas, National Shrine of Our Lady of Perpetual Help in Parañaque, National Shrine and Parish of St. Jude Thaddeus in Manila, Monasterio de Sta. Clara in Quezon City, Pink Sisters Convent in Tagaytay City, and the National Shrine and Cathedral of Our Lady of Peace and Good Voyage in Antipolo, Rizal. In the Cagayan Valley region, a noted pilgrimage site to include is the Iguig Calvary Hills in Cagayan, and in the province of Nueva Vizcaya, the Bangan Hill National Park also acts as a pilgrimage site where the Passion of the Christ is re-enacted during the holy week. The components of a pilgrimage site include the religious element like, a significant religious-related event that may have happened in the past, and further, possessing the pristine features enabling a reflective mood for the pilgrims and anyone who intends to visit it.

Challenges encountered by Pilgrimage Sites

Despite the benefits brought about by the tourism activities to the community, challenges are also faced by these sites. The development of religious tourism must be addressed with caution to be a sustainable and responsible socio-cultural activity, to avoid any commodification of the site and over-commercialization of souvenirs (Zarb, 2020).

In a study conducted by Shinde (2007), they found that pilgrimage tourism sites in India suffer from stress on basic services like water supply, sewerage, and solid waste. The increase in pollution also affects the environment especially for Tiruma and Tirupati sites in India due to the increase of traffic density related to the visitation patterns. Exploitation of natural resources was also identified that brought imbalance to the natural environment. The flora and fauna were disturbed due to noise pollution and traffic congestion brought by pilgrims.

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Similarly, in a pilgrimage site in the Philippines, the Fort Pilar Shrine suffers from congestion, waste segregation, and commercialization brought on by the increasing number of pilgrims visiting the site (Tenedero, 2023). Further, it is also a common observation that destination sites like pilgrimage sites and even those which are not, experienced being left with wastes or trash improperly being disposed of or scattered on various zones of the location, leaving an unpleasant sight to behold. Undeniably, this is one of the most observable challenges that tourism sites experience, and pilgrimage sites are not excused.

Other challenges shared by Zivrali (2022) are inflation and economic leakages, dependence on tourism, commercialization of tradition, cultural deterioration, and environmental damages.

Community-based Sustainable Tourism (CBST)

Community-based Tourism strategies can help enhance faith-based or religious sites and activities through added value to the visitors because of direct interaction with the host community. This experience will deliver authentic and unique concepts for the visitors to observe and experience. Host community and local businesses are also given ownership of the strategy and policy development of the community. Consultation of the stakeholders is exercised through dialogue (Zarb, 2020).

The community-based tourism uses a bottom-up approach for sustainable development to enhance the protection of natural and cultural resources and to generate income at the local level (Yamashita, n.d.). The importance of consulting the stakeholders before the creation and implementation of plans and programs will help the tourism planners identify important details that the stakeholders and residents know. It involves communities in aspects of tourism ranging from planning to active participation to seek their support to provide authentic local experience. However, lack of sustainable planning can also create adverse effects in local communities (Zivrali, 2022).

C. Theoretical Framework

Stakeholders Theory

Stakeholder theory (ST) is a theory of business ethics and organizational management (Schaltegger et al., 2019). According to ST, organizations aim to generate multiple benefits for different stakeholders (i.e., groups and individuals who can affect or be affected by the organization—e.g., civil societies, communities, customers, employees, governments, shareholders, suppliers) (Freeman, 1984). With the Stakeholders Theory, everyone, either an

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individual or group of individuals who have a stake in a particular entity contributes his or their resources with the aim of achieving the desired outcomes for the entity or organization being referred to. Thus, similar to any community-based engagement the collaborative efforts from the members of the community, considering the stake each one has to contribute, is expected to be provided arriving at an expected result from the engagement. In the context of this current study, it is then seen as relevant that the Stakeholders Theory holds a connection in providing the needed descriptions and explaining the picture of how the site being studied, the Mangkelleb Hill, eventually came into how it is today, and what the management aspires it to be.

D. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

This study, as presented on the first box on the figure below will be describing the Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site and determine the challenges the management encounters in managing the site. Succeeding on the second box is the conduct of site visits and interviews or focus group discussions (whichever will be amenable for the informants). The third box pertains to the crafting of an appropriate plan of action aiming for the further development of the pilgrimage site as will be partly taken from the recommendations solicited from the informants, and on what the researchers would be able to find and conclude. These recommendations are aimed to be forwarded or shared to the parish which is directly supervising the site.

The Research Paradigm

E. Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

This study generally aimed at describing Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site, its challenges encountered to have it developed as a known pilgrimage site in the province, and craft a recommended plan of actions for the realization of the project's further development. The responses of key stakeholders in the community where the site is located were solicited to provide answers to the set objectives. This study was conducted on the first semester of the academic year 2024-2025. Particularly, this study sought answers to the following objectives:

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1. describe the Magkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site;
2. narrate how the site has been since the start of the project up to date;
3. identify the challenges the management faces in developing the site as a known pilgrimage site in the province of Nueva Vizcaya; and
4. present an action plan that will guide the management in realizing the site to be a pilgrimage site.

Methodology

A. Design

This research is primarily qualitative in nature. Qualitative because it intends to describe Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site since the start of its initial development up to its current state and identify the challenges encountered to have it developed as a known pilgrimage site in the province. An intended result is the crafting of a-recommended plan of action for the realization of the project's further development. Further, it is qualitative as the solicited responses or descriptions from the selected and invited informants regarding the pilgrimage site, will be analyzed to suit the set objectives of the study. The gathering of data were done through the conduct of interviews and focus group discussions. Results from the conducted interviews and focus group discussions were summarized, interpreted, and narrated by the researchers. The results of the analysis were presented through the storyboarding technique and were supported by related studies and literature. This technique used for this study made the research method qualitative.

B. Locale

The research locale was at the town of Villaverde, where the Mangkelleb Hill is located. Villaverde is one among the fifteen (15) towns of the lone district of Nueva Vizcaya, which also shares the pristine beauty and serene ambiance of the province known to be the watershed haven of the north. Apart from the natural beauty, religiosity wise, the town is also home to the Our Lady of Fatima Parish, and the Mangkelleb Hill, regarded as pilgrimage site in the town, under the management of the parish. Mangkelleb Hill or also known as Our Lady of Victory Pilgrimage Site was known among the parishioners as Calvary Hill and used as site during Good Friday of Holy Week Celebration among Roman Catholics.

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Source: Google Map

C. Participants and Sample

Participants considered in this study were the stakeholders where the Mangkelleb Hill is located. These informants were: three (3) members of the Knights of Columbus; one (1) Sangguniang Bayan Member in charge of Tourism; one (1) Barangay Captain; one (1) Purok Leader; four (4) residents; three (3) pilgrims; and three (3) parish council members, who were referred to by the Barangay Captain or the Purok Leader. The above-mentioned stakeholders were identified in consideration of their extent of knowledge about Mangkelleb Hill and their extent of involvement in the endeavors conducted for the hill itself as a pilgrimage site.

D. Instrument(s)

As for the first research objective, this was addressed by relevant documents the researchers sourced from credible sources, particularly from the Our Lady of Fatima Parish in Villaverde. Thus, no instrument is necessary to be utilized. For the second and third objectives, an interview or focus group discussion (FGD) guide questions that were self-made were utilized. The crafted interview guide questions were based from the sociological approach which variables are on social structure, culture and history. The interview guide questions were validated by a panel of experts, including the University Research Director and invited experts.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

The identified informants were contacted first through their social media accounts (Facebook Messenger) and through referrals as aided by the people from the parish, informing them that they are requested to be part of the study, and thus a personal appointment was also requested for initial meeting. With their response, the researchers asked for a convenient date and time for an initial meeting, where the

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research objectives were discussed. Given that a date and time were set, it was on this schedule that the informed consent form were presented and explained. With their agreement or provision of consent, the interview or Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were conducted right away, then the session started. Otherwise, the researcher needed to adhere to another convenient date and time for the sessions to take place. During the interviews and/or FGD, the researchers asked permission for the sessions to be audio-recorded for transcribing purposes. With this, the researchers facilitated the session and later transcribed the recordings, that will be used for the analysis. The individuals who gave their consent were given assurance that they were free to withdraw should they wish and that this will not be taken against them. Thus, initially taken information will be excluded in the study.

F. Treatment of Data

This study employed the qualitative type of research, wherein the data were taken through document scanning, observation during site visits, and one-on-one interviews and/or Focus Group Discussions. Data gathered from the interviews / FGDs with identified informants were converted into transcriptions. With this, content analysis were used to convert qualitative data to quantitative data.

The original data were in the form of recordings taken when the interviews / FGDs were conducted. The set sessions proceeded immediately with the use of the crafted interview guide. Responses were analyzed thematically. Content and narrative analysis were utilized as well. Meanings of data derived from the use of the interview guide for the group discussions and interviews were likewise examined to establish a list of possible tourism projects and activities that may respond to the fourth objective of the research.

G. Ethical Considerations

A letter requesting permission to conduct the study shall be addressed to the pre-selected stakeholders where the Mangkelleb Hill is located. The purpose and the significance of the study will be discussed with the concerned informants. The schedule of the conduct of interviews or focus group discussions, whichever will be feasible, will be settled considering the availability of the invited informants.

Consent to participate in the study will be asked from the informants, by affixing their signatures on the informed consent form signifying their voluntary participation. Moreover, the names of the informants will not be mentioned in the study, unless they are willing to disclose their identities. It is then ensured that confidentiality is observed for both the researchers and also for those involved in the interviews or FGDs. Further, information and data gathered will only be kept and accessed by the researchers in a particular drive. This information or data would only be permanently deleted once the study has been finished, presented at

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the university, and finally submitted as finished research. Permission to audio and video record the interview or focus group discussion will be asked; thus, consent will be signed before the conduct of the interview and FGD.

The interview/FGD guide questions will undergo content validation by a panel of experts. Information and ideas coming from various authors have been cited throughout the paper using the APA citation style.

In addition, a letter requesting for relevant documents and information will be addressed to the Parish which the pilgrimage site is under supervision or management. The purpose and significance of the study will be discussed in the request letter. Once the request is approved, the solicitation of the necessary documents and information will be done at the convenient time of the involved personnel in the above-mentioned office. All requested information will be properly cited and referenced on the study.

There will be no known risk in the informants' participation to the study and there will be no direct benefit to them either. In this case, there is no conflict of interest declared in this study. However, informants will contribute to the creation of new knowledge about the challenges the Magkelleb Hill encountered following its development, and the crafting of a plan of actions that may thereby be significant to the management which has direct jurisdiction on the pilgrimage site.

Further, the results of the study will be shared to the Parish itself, that it may serve its purpose of assisting the management in moving forward to how the site be further developed. The study may also be submitted for research fora and for publication of its extended abstract on the SMU website, and other relevant publication/s.

Section 1: Mangkelleb Hill as a Pilgrimage Site

Mangkelleb Hill has been named as such attributing to two rocks merged or put over the other, as located in the hill's peak. According to the informants, the term came from the Iloco dialect "kelleb" or in English, "put together". This name, Mangkelleb Hill, has been the known name, and no written records so far about its history are searched, except for the usual stories of the town's constituents, particularly the elderlies, whose parents or relatives had passed the story down to their children.

Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto is a unique site that embodies both natural and cultural/historical attractions. The site features a combination of breathtaking landscapes when atop, that include surrounding majestic mountains and highlands, which provide a stunning backdrop for visitors once arriving at its peak. In addition to its natural beauty, the built landscape, as exemplified by the Grotto dedicated to Our Lady of the Holy Rosary,

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enhances the cultural and historical significance of the area. It is observed though that further enhancement to add more on its aesthetic feature is possible. The harmonious blend of natural and built environments makes Mangkelleb a potential compelling destination for those seeking to explore both the scenic wonders and rich heritage of Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya, particularly, barangay Ibung, where this Grotto is situated. Though Stainton (2023) indicated that pilgrimage tourism, which Mangkelleb Hill's stewards are trying it to be positioned for in the tourism context, is an old type of tourism practiced embedded with visits on religious destinations such as churches, mosques and other landmarks, the Mangkelleb Hill may be considered as an essential landform that motivates visitors to better appreciate and commune with their religion, partaking in certain practice such as being involved in a walk conducted on Good Fridays. Similarly, monasteries and churches from Valcea County in South-West Oltenia Region, Romania are also for religious tourism and pilgrimage purpose and are representing major historical and cultural elements for the location's identity and attractiveness (Drăguleasa et. al., 2024).

Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto Pilgrim Site is both a historical and cultural site, steeped in rich narratives that blend faith, legend, and community heritage. This location is renowned for its Grotto dedicated to Our Lady of the Holy Rosary, also referred to as Nuestra Señora del Santo Rosario and, by some, as Our Lady of Victory. The Grotto, beautifully situated to overlook the Town of Villaverde, serves as a scenic landmark infused with spiritual significance. It has become a focal point for the annual dramatization of the Via Crucis or Stations of the Cross, reflecting the deep-rooted religious traditions of the community. Parishioners described the place like a church. This year 2025, a new venue for these dramatizations has been identified, further enhancing the site's cultural importance. Mangkelleb Grotto stands as a mountain of hope and a testament to the devotion to the Blessed Mother, encouraging visitors to connect with the community's religious history while journeying with Christ toward Calvary. It is a sacred space for prayer, reflection, and the celebration of faith, inviting all to partake in its beautiful story and spiritual heritage. From the road going up to the grotto may take around 15 minutes of regular walking with more or less a climb of 250 steps, around 200 steps paved and the rest still unpaved.

In history, Villaverde, before its creation as a town, was formerly a Barrio of Solano, which was called IBUNG founded by a Dominican Friar named Alejandro Vidad, a Spanish Missionary Priest in 1767. On May 28, 1957, an order was issued organizing Ibung as a Town by Father Juan Villaverde, thus making it the town of Villaverde. When the American Government was established in the Province, Ibung lost its identity as a town because of its insufficient funds and small population. The people transferred to other places because of the fear of the barbaric non-Christian tribes living in the nearby mountains. Ibung then became again a mere barangay of the Municipality of Solano (<https://villaverde-nvizcaya.gov.ph/barangays-of-villaverde/barangay-ibung/>).

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Section 2: Mangkelleb Hill Before and Now

The Mangkelleb Hill is a typical landform in the municipality of Villaverde. It is a site quite near from several households in the central town of this town, and is located particularly in Purok 6 of Brgy. Ibung. From the stories shared by the informants, the hill is privately owned by several individuals on several portions. At present, it is being managed by the Parish of Our Lady of Fatima (OLV) – Villaverde and its school with the Knights of Columbus, a mutual benefit society for a membership of practicing male Catholics, providing support services to Catholic institutions among others. The Parish of OLV owns four (4) hectares portion of the hill including the summit which provides a vantage point to appreciate a 360 degree view of the surrounding fields and towns of Solano and Bagabag. As portions of the hill are owned by individuals, in the spirit of generosity, Llagas and Obra Families had donated a right of way where the paved stairs going up are located. Further, with the shared efforts from the residents, the Knights of Columbus, *Purok* leaders from where the hill is located, the hill is occasionally being managed in terms of keeping it tended, especially weeks before an organized church activity. This includes the holy week in March or April of the year, likewise the birthday of Mama Mary every September.

Photo above is a snapshot of the annual conduct of the “Stations of the Cross” in the early 2010s. The re-enactment is held on the foot of the hill, with permission from the landowners. For three years now, the re-enactment goes up to the hill’s summit, starting from the Our Lady of Fatima Parish.

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Photo above is a snapshot of the annual conduct of the “Stations of the Cross” in the early 2010s. The re-enactment is held on the foot of the hill, with permission from the landowners. For three years now, the re-enactment goes up to the hill’s summit, starting from the Our Lady of Fatima Parish.

On left photo is the Mangkelleb Hill’s present entrance view just along the road, and on right is around 100 steps going up the summit.

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Photos above are glimpses of the hill's summit during the re-enactment of Christ's Passion on Good Friday of 2024.

Shown on this photo is a grotto taken March of 2024 put up through the efforts of the Knights of Columbus.

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The current state of the hill is a result of bayanihan among its residents. The concreted footpath had eventually carried out with concerted labor among volunteers and donations of materials from generous donors, leading to its completion by February 14, 2020.

Though it is noted that physical developments on the hill is observed, there are at least few features which were being included overtime. In other locations, visits to sites for religious and pilgrimage tourism purposes are growing in interest among people worldwide. This is true in the case of Slovakia, wherein attendance analysis revealed a significant upward trend on sacred sites (Jesensky et.al., 2024). This implies collaboration is necessary in ensuring the sustainability of historically significant sites for further local development.

Section 3: Challenges the Management Encountered in Developing Mangkelleb Hill as a Pilgrimage Site in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya

Just like any project being developed, corresponding challenges are inevitably encountered. In the case of Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site, noted challenges were shared by the informants. Primarily, the challenges boil to the difficulty of acquiring the much needed resources to commence necessary tasks in putting up structures that are deemed important for a site to be appealing to visitors. Resources include financial essential in the purchase of materials that would add up in the site's physical improvement. Another resource includes manpower, which comprises the team who will be enacting labor to put in place certain materials and to include as well landscaping or beautifying with appropriate flora which can contribute to the visual appeal of the site. Most of the manpower support are coming from the Knights of Columbus (K of C) members that provide additional support in the beautification and cleaning of the site.

With the current condition of the pilgrimage site, an additional challenge is the routine of its proper maintenance. The informants, though, disclose that extension activities of a private university somehow provide occasional site keeping in the form of planting additional ornamental plants alongside the stairs and posting informative materials promoting sustainability and green efforts. These efforts are well appreciated. However, it is recognized that additional schedules for site-keeping need to be in place.

Destinations should become more accessible, more sustainable, and ultimately more competitive (Dimanche & Andrades, 2024). Current challenges for tourism destination management are on how to make the site sustainable, and a competitive tourist site. Moreover, Dimanche & Andrades (2024) said that challenges in developing site can be solved through incorporating innovation and technology as driving levers for more effective, transparent, cooperative, and participatory governance; (2) by committing to sustainability; (3) by providing universal accessibility and quality tourist experiences, (4) to improve the well-being of the resident population, and (5) to preserve the tangible and intangible natural and cultural heritage. Through this, accessibility and sustainability of the place can be secured. Accessibility-wise, Mangkelleb Hill is provided with a paved

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municipal road up to its entrance, and these roads are considered convenient for vehicles and so with the usual biking or a walk for those who prefer.

In relation to financial resources for development, the most challenging part of a religious tourism site is the separation of the church and the government. This is viewed as “High Wall” by Roger Williams, a Puritan minister who founded a new form of government based on this idea (National Park Service, 2023). In the Philippines, the separation of the juridical functions of the church and the government is stated in the 1987 constitution article 11 Section 1-6. To note, this provision of the law even extends to the separation of funding to different projects with the church. Hence, no funds should be allocated to the different projects of any religion or church organization.

In the case of Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto Pilgrim Site, the only support of the Barangay LGU that it can provide is the manpower support through the **TUPAD** (*Tulong Panghanapbuhay sa Ating Disadvantaged/Displaced Workers*) program of the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) where local community members clean the surrounding of the grotto for maintenance. Hence, the challenges encountered in Mangkelleb may also be explained by the research conducted by Soljan and Liro (2020) due to some contractions between the spiritual character of the pilgrimage site and the secular need for effective management to gain economic benefits.

With the usual challenge on the regular physical maintenance of the hill, a private university in the province through its Tourism Management program had made a Memorandum of Agreement sealing extension activities to be provided to Mangkelleb Hill. Scheduled clean-up drive with students and their advisers were set with the value of community extension and volunteerism aimed at being instilled among the tertiary students, thereby providing help to this considered, adopt-a-tourist site as a school project.

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Shown above are the Department Head, Professors and Students at the welcome signage of the Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto, before commencing site cleaning from the street up to the hill. These are students from Sustainable Tourism & Ecotourism classes from the University.

In the above photo are students on a clean-up drive activity in the vicinity of the Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto.

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The donated solar lights were officially handed over to Our Lady of Fatima Parish in Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya, supporting the community's sustainability efforts.

A roundtable discussion explored future projects, including candle-making and other product development initiatives.

Section 4: Proposed Action for the Development of Mangkelleb Hill as a Pilgrimage Site in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya

With the Our Lady of Victory Calvary Hill and Grotto Pilgrim Site as a Pilgrimage Site being described in this paper, its past and current picture, and with the surfaced challenges the Management encountered in further developing the property as a known pilgrimage site in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya, a proposed Action Plan is drafted for review and potential adoption which may contribute to a sustained development for the site. The following contains the proposed activities with corresponding details:

Proposed Action Plan for the Development of Mangkelleb Hill as a Pilgrimage Site

Objectives	Tasks	Success Criteria	Time Frame	Resources
Creation of a dedicated committee from the parish which will oversee the Mangkelleb Hill as a Pilgrimage Site.	General meeting with the stakeholders to commence an organization or committee that will focus on the maintenance and development of the hill.	Committee overseeing the Mangkelleb Hill's Development is formed.	2 Months	Parish Pastoral Council
Sustaining linkage with the HEI's HTM Department re marketing efforts.	Maintain linkage with the HEI's HTM Department re marketing efforts.	Active Memorandum of Agreement	3 months	Parish Pastoral Council
Provision of a Welcome Arc at the foot of the Hill.	Solicit ideas for the welcome arc. Plan on the sourcing out of funds. Construction of the welcome arc itself. Request assistance from a University's Department of Architecture for the design assistance as an extension activity.	Built new welcome arc.	12 months	Sponsorships from generous constituents. Barangay Leaders
Construction and development of the Stations of the Cross going to the top area of the grotto.	Plan on the sourcing out of funds. Construction of the stations of the cross.	Built 12 stations of the cross on the slope of Mangkelleb Hill.	18 months	Donations from constituents. Barangay Leaders
Improvement of the stairs going to Mama Mary.	Plan on the sourcing out of funds. Construction of the paved stairs.	Enhanced paved stairs	12 months	Donations from constituents. Labor from Institution/s providing extension activities.

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Development of the altar and the shade for gathering.	Plan on the sourcing out of funds. Construction of the altar and shades.	Built/enhanced altar and shade.	12 months	Donations from constituents. Barangay Leaders
Development of the Bubon by the Lorenzo Family	Construction of support features for the <i>Bubon</i> (well).	Built supporting features for the <i>Bubon</i> (well).	6 months	Donations from constituents
Resolution for pushing cycling as an activity for Villaverde enroute Bagabag, with the Mangkelleb Hill as a pitstop.	Meeting with the Parish, LGU of Villaverde and Tourism and Culture Office of Nueva Vizcaya on the proposed development of the cycling tourism in the area.	Proposed plan for cycling tourism development in Villaverde.	3 months	Sangguniang Bayan of Villaverde Villaverde Parish Provincial Tourism and Culture Office
Integration of livelihood program for local community members within and surrounding the Mangkelleb Hill Area.	Meeting with SMU-HTM Department and TESDA for the applicable livelihood trainings for the residents within and surrounding the Mangkelleb Hill Area.	Crafted livelihood program.	12 months	Utilization of Active Linkage with the Private Sector that is, HEIs

In the study of Chuajap et. al. (2024), they have created a framework that was based on the sustainable religious tourism management of Marian Shrines in the Philippines. They have identified four (4) themes which are the Immersion, Stewardship, Tutelage, and Proposition. They suggest that Marian Shrines could use this framework in establishing a sustainable tourist destination. This may be considered by the management of Mangkelleb Hill, noting on stewardship ensuring collective efforts among its stakeholders in providing care for the site.

Immersion is where locals and tourists are motivated by their devotion and spiritual wellness. The collaboration between different sectors creates awareness and partnerships that benefit everyone involved. Examples of these are spiritual wellness, artistic value by artists, feeding programs and coordination of committees with government. Stewardship focuses on recognizing the practices of Marian Shrine in maintaining and supporting their facilities, people and operations. Considering that these are NGOs, they get support from donations, store income and voluntary contributions. Example of this are the mass donation, income from products sold by the church and GCash movements. Tutelage focuses on the protection and security of the shrines and the people. Clean-up drive activities, proper waste disposal and anti-littering campaigns are some examples of this theme. The last one is proposition. It centres to the opportunities set by religious tourism, sustainability, development plans, and recommendations to improve the shrines and their surroundings.

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Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions. Based from the findings, the researchers arrive at these conclusions:

1. The Mangkelleb Hill is a thriving local pilgrimage site in the town of Villaverde in Nueva Vizcaya, managed by the local parish church of Our Lady of Fatima Villaverde.
2. Though the hill has been present witnessing events overtime in the locality, it has been the same hill with additional enhancements on its landscape and concreted stairs going up to the grotto.
3. The challenges the Management faced in the development of the site basically boils down to the lack, or even absence of source of funds that will be essential in the installation of needed physical enhancement to present the hill as a more pleasing pilgrimage site.
4. An action plan that will guide the management in realizing the site to be an enhanced pilgrimage site is concluded necessary that may aid in the enhancement of Mangkelleb Hill.

Recommendations. The proposed action plan is recommended to be presented to the Parish of Villaverde for their review and possible adoption.

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Appendices

**Appendix A
 Informed Consent Form**

This form is for identified stakeholders where the Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site is located, in relation to their participation to the research project entitled, **“Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization”**.

Name of Researchers: Covita, Mayvelyn S.
 Ibarra, John Michael C.
 Soriano, Mark Ian J.
 Costales, Crispin A.

Organizational Affiliation: Saint Mary’s University
 School of Accountancy and Business
 Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management

Information Sheet

You are being invited by the above researchers of Saint Mary’s University to participate in their study regarding the Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site. You can take your time to decide whether to participate or not and you can ask questions any time for any word or concept in this form that you may not understand.

The purpose of this study is to describe the Mangkelleb Hill as a pilgrimage site since the start of its initial development up to its current state, identify the challenges encountered to have it developed as a known pilgrimage site in the province, and craft a recommended plan of actions for the realization of the project’s further development

This study involves the conduct of interviews and/or focus-group discussions. Several guide questions will be raised during the interview or FGD. In case there is difficulty in understanding the ICF and the questions in English, the researchers will assist in providing explanations to the Informants for them to better and clearly understand. You are selected as one of the informants as one of the stakeholders where the hill is located. You are one among the ten (10) selected informants.

Should you choose to participate in the study, you shall be answering the guide questions during the interview / FGD on a scheduled date which will be set on your most convenient time, to be held on a face-to-face modality.

It is estimated that your participation in the study will only take around 45 minutes. There is no known risk in your participation to the study. You will contribute to the creation of new knowledge about the challenges the Magkelleb Hill encountered following its

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development, and the crafting of a plan of actions that may thereby be significant to the management which has direct jurisdiction on the pilgrimage site.

You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements. However, as gratitude for your participation through interview / FGD, simple snacks will be provided.

Kindly be assured that in case of your refusal to participate or discontinue at any time, this will not involve penalty or loss of benefits to which you as research participants are entitled.

Thus, even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue and any information you have already provided will not be used in the study. Rest assured that your privacy will be respected and all your answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality. The recorded and will be transcribed interview / FGD sessions will be saved accordingly and only the researchers can have access on these, and as your identity will be known both by the researchers and those involved in the FGD, your identity will be anonymized by providing you a number code instead of your name/email. The data you will provide will be transcribed in MS Word document. Except for the researchers, no one will be able to identify you as informants in this study. After the study is completed and finally presented and submitted to the University Research Center, all the data in the Google drive and in each researcher's computers / laptops will be deleted for good.

The results of this study may be disseminated within Saint Mary's University through faculty research fora. Also, the study may be submitted for publication in national or international journals. For any matter concerning this study, you can contact Dr. Mayvelyn S. Covita through the following mobile number: 09988892968 or email: mcovita@smu.edu.ph.

This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be an informant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]

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Statement of the Person Taking the Informed Consent

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the informant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the informant understands that the following will be done:

1. S/he participates in the interview and/or FGD session/s and thus provides answers to the questions the researchers will raise.

I confirm that the participant has been allowed to ask questions and that his/her queries have been answered correctly to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this informed consent form has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of Researcher: _____

Signature of Researcher: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]

Appendix B **Interview / FGD Guide Questions**

1. How and when did Mangkelleb Hill get its name?
2. Which supervises the management of the Hill?
3. Particularly, who are the individuals or organizations involved in maintaining the Hill?
4. Kindly describe how did it start? What notable activities/events had been held in here throughout the years?
5. Approximately how many visitors come to the hill and on what occasions? On what particular period of the year do visitors most come?
6. What difficulties were encountered in making Magkelleb Hill of what it is today?
7. So far, what has been done to address the difficulties/challenges the Mangkelleb Hill encounters?
8. What do you further suggest, can help solve the problems/ challenges that the Mangkelleb Hill experiences?
9. What future plans do you have in mind for the Mangkelleb Hill?

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Appendix C Ethical Clearance Certificate

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
 BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS OFFICE

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ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

This certifies that the following protocol and related documents have been approved, monitored, and granted clearance by SMUREB.

SMUREB Code: 2024 0629
Research Proponent/s: MAYVELYN S. COVITA, PhD
 JOHN MICHAEL C. IBARRA
 MARK IAN J. SORIANO
 FR. CRISPIN A. COSTALES
Title: Faithful Stewardship: A Community-Centric Pilgrimage Site Revitalization

Protocol Version No.: 2
Version Date: July 18, 2024
ICF Version No.: 2
Version Date: July 18, 2024
Type of Review: Expedited

The research proponent has submitted the final report form and has complied with all the requirements of the Research Ethics Board.

Issued and signed on May 6, 2025.

JASON ARNOLD L. MASLANG
 Chair, SMUREB

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 Driven by Excellence*

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I. General information		
Name	Mayvelyn S. Covita	
Date of birth:	July 15, 1981	
Contact number:	09988892968	
Email address:	mcovita@smu.edu.ph	
Address:	Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	
Affiliation:	Name of Department: HTM Department and School of Graduate Studies	Name of Institution: Saint Mary's University
Position:	Graduate Program Cluster Department Head for Business and Accountancy	Specialty: Hospitality and Tourism Management
II. Educational Background		
Name of Institution:	Course/Degree:	Year/s attended:
Saint Mary's University Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	PhD in Commerce	2009-2017
Philippine Women's University Taft Avenue, Manila	MBA with Specialization in Tourism Management	2006-2008
Saint Mary's University Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	BS in Tourism	1999-2003
III. Research Related Trainings Including Research Ethics:		
Name of Course:	Offered by:	Year:
Training Workshop on Writing for Publication	SMU University Research Center	February 27, 2024
Good Research Practice Training (GRPT)	Philippine Health Research Ethics Board and Philippine Council for Health Research and Development, Department of Science and Technology	January 10-11, 2024
Research Colloquium cum Extension in celebration of the Linggo ng Likha at Lingkod with the theme, "Manawari: Changing Minds, Charting Directions onward SMU @100"	Saint Mary's University School of Graduate Studies	April 29, 2023 via Zoom
Webinar on Using Reliable Online Resources in Research in celebration of the Linggo ng Likha at Lingkod with the theme, "Manawari: Changing Minds, Charting Directions onward SMU @100"	Saint Mary's University URC, SOGS and LMCDAC	April 26, 2023

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Road to Publication Session 2: "Ethical Issues, Charges in Journal Publishing and Searching for Reputable Journals" via Zoom	SMU School of Graduate Studies	July 3, 2021
Road to Publication Session 1: "Manuscript Preparation for Publication" via Zoom	SMU School of Graduate Studies	June 26, 2021
Basic Research Ethics Training	PHREB & SMU	January 12-13, 2021
Webinar: Experience It, Learn It, Use It - Model online lessons with National Geographic Learning Tourism: Writing a Questionnaire	National Geographic	November 26, 2020
Webinar: "Postgraduate Sharing & Learning 2: Research Topic Generation for Hospitality and Tourism Postgraduate Students"	Universiti Teknologi Mara (Malaysia), APCORE, PARTH	August 6, 2020
Webinar: Changes in Hospitality Management and Research	Organizer: UP Diliman DHRIM	August 6, 2020
AAHRMEI Webinar Series Part II: "Research Made Easy: Avoiding Common Mistakes on Writing Thesis and Dissertation Proposal"	Association of Administrators in Hospitality, Hotel and Restaurant Management Educational Institutions (AAHRMEI)	July 18, 2020
Seminar-Workshop on Doing Research in a Way That Counts: Intellectual Property as a Research Output	University Research Center of SMU	January 16-17, 2020
Seminar-Workshop on Doing Research in a Way That Counts: Writing for Publication	University Research Center of SMU	January 8-10, 2020
IV. Research Outputs		
Title of research	Year and Author/s	Published/Unpublished
Heritage-Related Resources in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines as Potential Heritage Tourism Sites	Covita et.al., 2023	Unpublished
Safety and Security of Paragliding as a Recreational Activity	Covita et.al., 2023	Unpublished
Engaged Recreational Activities in the Pandemic: Their Impact on Tourism Students' Performance	Covita et.al., 2023	Unpublished
Benefits and Concerns Arising from Virtual Reality in Tourism	Covita et.al., 2022	Unpublished
Challenges and Strategies of Farm Tourism Sites in Quirino Province	Covita et.al., 2022	Unpublished
Guest Satisfaction on Accommodation Facility in the New Normal: An Importance-Performance Analysis	Covita et.al., 2022	Unpublished
Awareness, Practices and Issues gearing toward Green Technology among DOT Accredited Accommodation Facilities in a Northern Philippine Province	Covita et.al., 2020	Unpublished
A Preliminary Assessment of Flower Farms in Kayapa: Their Potentials as Farm Tourism Destinations in Northern Philippines (under the DOT Tourism Research Grant 2018)	Covita, 2019	Unpublished
Employment Conditions of Saint Mary's University's HRM and Tourism Graduates from 2003-2015: Contributions to the Tourism Industry	Covita et.al., 2017	Unpublished
Practices and Issues on Sustainable Tourism in Selected Municipalities of Nueva Vizcaya	Covita, 2017	Published
The Momma Practice of Ifugao People: Implication to Tourism	Covita et.al., 2016	Unpublished
Problems and Coping Strategies of SMU-HTM Students During Their US Cultural Exchange	Covita & Torres, 2016	Unpublished

Experience: Basis for an Enhanced Preparation of Students for International Internship Program		
Ecotourism as a strategy for sustainable development in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines.	Covita, 2009	Published
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<i>Name of Institution:</i>	<i>Course/Degree:</i>	<i>Year/s attended:</i>
SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY	BS HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT MAJOR IN HOTEL, RESORT AND RESTAURANT MANAGEMENT, MINOR IN TOUR AND TRAVEL	2007-2013
PHILIPPINE WOMENS UNIVERSITY AND ITS AFFILIATE SCHOOL OF MEN	MASTER OF SCIENCE IN HOTEL AND RESTUARANT MANAGEMENT	2014-2019
III. Research Related Trainings Including Research Ethics within the last 5 years		
<i>Name of Course:</i>	<i>Offered by:</i>	<i>Actual Date:</i>
Training Workshop on Writing for Publication	SMU University Research Center	February 27, 2024

<i>Sustainable and Innovative Knowledge Application for Tourism (SIKAT) funded by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED)</i>	<i>University of Alicante Spain</i>	July 2021 and October 2023
5 th Philippine Research Conference on Tourism and Hospitality	University of the Philippines-Diliman, Asian Institute of Tourism	October 28-29, 2022
Seminar-Workshop on doing research in a way that counts: Intellectual Property as a Research Output	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong Nueva Vizcaya	January 17, 2020
Seminar-Workshop on doing research in a way that counts: Writing for Publication	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong Nueva Vizcaya	January 10, 2020

IV. Description of Past and Present Research Involvement (Summary of Research Topics, both published and unpublished)

Title of research	Year and Author/s	Published/Unpublished
Strategies Employed by Restaurants in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya to Survive the Impact of Pandemic	June 2023	Unpublished
Expectation vs. Reality: Food Service, Price and Promotion of Fast-Food Restaurant	June 2023	Unpublished
The Effectiveness of Travel Vloggers on the Decision-Making of Tourist in Visiting Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines	February 2022	Unpublished
Sensory Acceptability of Mulberry, Malungay and Lagundi Tea	June 2022	Unpublished
Accommodation Facilities in the New Normal: an Analysis of the Coping Mechanism of Hospitality Establishments Towards Business Sustainability	August 2021	Unpublished
Documentation of Pinikpikan as a Traditional Food of Nagtipunan, Quirino Province	June 2019	Unpublished
Acceptability of Deconstructed Atsara Bamboo Shoot Stuffed with Dinengdeng as a New Local Dish of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	July 2019	Unpublished
Acceptability of Yacun Jam	July 2019	Unpublished
Acceptability of Banana Peel Yema	August 2019	Unpublished
The Acceptability of Satsuma Moringa Crème Glacee	June 2019	Unpublished
Acceptability of Taro Cookies as an Innivative Product of Nueva Vizcaya	May 2019	Unpublished
Sensory Acceptability of Eel Chicharon as a Local Product	June 2019	Unpublished
General Acceptability of Coconut Sugar Syrup	May 2019	Unpublished
Governor's Rapids Tourist Satisfaction	June 2018	Unpublished
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II. Educational Background		
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Philippine Women's University	Master of Science in Tourism Management	2014-2016
Saint Louis University	Bachelor of Science in Hospitality and Tourism Management	2008-2012
III. Research Related Trainings Including Research Ethics within the last 5 years		
<i>Name of Course:</i>	<i>Offered by:</i>	<i>Actual Date:</i>
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IV. Description of Past and Present Research Involvement (Summary of Research Topics, both published and unpublished)		

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<p>Author</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable Community-based Tourism: Case of the Municipality of Sagada, Mt. Province (2019) • Motivations of Solo Filipino Travelers: A Market Research (2019) <p>Promoter-Adviser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malico, Nueva Vizcaya as a Sustainable Tourism Destination (2023) • Challenges of farm Tourism Sites in Nueva Vizcaya: Paitan Flower Farm and La Fortuna Farm (2023) • Level of Skills Competencies of Tourism Management Students (2023) • Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya as a Farm Tourism Destination: Basis for Post-Pandemic Tourism Branding (2023) • Gastronomical Treasures of Nueva Vizcaya: A Study of Awareness and Potentialities as a Tourist Attraction (2023) • Evaluating Casat Falls in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya: A Local Tourism Gem (ongoing) • Residents' Level of Knowledge and Appreciation for St. Dominic Cathedral as a Heritage Site, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya (ongoing) • Empowering Communities: Unraveling the Nexus between Active Participation in Tourism Programs (ongoing) • Saint Mary's University Tertiary Students' Preferences of Farm Tourism Activities: Basis for Farm Tourism Product Development (ongoing) 	
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